

Well-being and Workplace Performance: A case of corporates in the region of Larache, Morocco

Le bien-être et performance au travail : cas des entreprises de la région de Larache, Maroc

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Abstract

Purpose: this paper sheds light on the positive association between people's well-being as an explanatory variable and work performance as a response variable. Based on the analysis and processing of data related to eight companies, using a quantitative method as part of an interpretivism epistemological position, we intended to seek how improving the state of well-being could increase work performance.

Design/methodology/approach: The survey data were collected from eight companies; seven are operating in the food industry and one in the metallurgy industry whose staff number exceeds 300 employees. The collected data were processed and analysed using a quantitative method as part of an interpretivist epistemological trend.

Findings: The empirical results indicate that a good state of well-being is a key factor in work performance. The social context is, in contrast, the most influential element when it comes to well-being; hence, strengthening employees' relationships at work is a facilitator of well-being. However, companies are still late in terms of capitalizing on well-being measures/indicators even though there is awareness about the importance of well-being for work performance.

Originality/Value: This study highlights the association between employees' well-being and work performance. By bringing that study down to the ground of Larache-Morocco, it allows researchers to conquer a new fertile zone.

Keywords – Employee well-being; workplace performance; social context; well-being-based performance; social performance.

Résumé

Objectif : cet article met en lumière l'association positive entre le bien-être des salariés en tant que variable explicative et la performance au travail en tant que variable à expliquer. A partir de l'analyse et traitement des données relatives à huit entreprises, à l'aide d'une méthode quantitative, dans le cadre d'un positionnement épistémologique interprétiviste, nous avons tenté de rechercher comment l'amélioration de l'état du bien-être pourrait augmenter la performance au travail.

Conception/méthodologie/approche : les données de l'enquête ont été recueillies auprès de huit entreprises ; sept opèrent dans l'industrie alimentaire et une dans l'industrie métallurgique dont l'effectif dépasse 300 salariés. Les données recueillies ont été traitées et analysées selon une méthode quantitative dans le cadre d'un courant épistémologique interprétativiste.

Résultats : Les résultats empiriques indiquent qu'un bon état de bien-être est un facteur clé de la performance au travail. Le contexte social est, en revanche, l'élément le plus influent en matière de bien-être ; ainsi, renforcer les relations des salariés au travail est un élément facilitateur du bien-être. Cependant, les entreprises tardent encore à capitaliser sur les mesures/indicateurs du bien-être même s'il existe une prise de conscience par rapport à l'importance du bien-être pour la performance au travail.

Originalité/Valeur : Cette étude met en évidence l'association entre le bien-être des employés et la performance au travail. En ramenant cette étude sur le terrain de Larache-Maroc, elle permet aux chercheurs de conquérir une nouvelle zone fertile.

Mots-clés – Bien-être des employés ; performance au travail ; contexte social ; performance au travail basée sur le bien-être ; performance sociale.

Introduction

Historically, the Hawthorne study, also called the Hawthorne effect, conducted from 1928 to 1932, has actually made the foundation stone of the human relations movement; that is why researchers' attention has been drawn to the issue of staff motivation (Tijani, 2011). Since then, a new shift in Human Resource Management (HRM) was embraced, placing the human capital state as the explanatory variable for various phenomena. In this framework, the association between employees' well-being and corporate performance is not a fertile research ground since previous theorists have already made their contributions at the micro and/or the macro levels such as utilitarians (Bentham, 1996; Mill, 1863). However, the core idea of considering the improvement of employees' state as the catalyst of work performance in Morocco is an interesting research ground that will shape interpretively the content of this scientific paper.

In fact, the utilitarian approach is an overall part of the resource-based theory that considers the human capital as the centre of an organization, and arguably the explanatory reason of positive organizational outcomes (Barney, 1991; McGee, 2015). This people-oriented approach explains organizational success based on internal sources rather than external ones.

The World Health Organization (World Health Organization, 2022) defines well-being as a "positive state experienced by individuals and societies" and considers it "similar to health" and therefore "a resource for daily life and is determined by social, economic and environmental conditions". In this semiotics, "well-being encompasses quality of life and the ability of people and societies to contribute to the world with a sense of meaning and purpose" (World Health Organization, 2022). That is why, the concepts of well-being, quality of life, and happiness at work are regarded with the glasses of contribution, in other terms, a well-being-based performance.

In this paper, we will highlight the role of insuring well-being for the unanimity of employees in increasing work performance. The utility principle that calls for "the greatest happiness for the greatest number" (Bentham, 1996) is exactly the general state of people's utility, felicity, or satisfaction that we will try to measure and associate with positive work performance. This purpose will be achieved using a quantitative method as part of an interpretivist posture. This epistemological choice is justified with the fact that this typology of scientific papers is already present in the literature, our mission, then, is to bring it down to Morocco, and especially to the region of Larache. For that, we are going to launch a literature review over different theoretical approaches that are relevantly in line with our subject, before conducting an empirical survey to collect data from eight companies in the matter. The collected data will be processed and

analysed based on a quantitative method as part of an interpretivist epistemological position. Hence, this study will channel its content toward the following research question: **How could the improvement of employees' well-being state increase work performance?**

Therefore, the first elements of this literature review will be focused on the employee well-being, and workplace performance, as well as the associations between both of the variables. And then, the methodology used will be launched before showing the paper's results that are going to be finished with a conclusion.

1. Literature Review

1.1. Employee well-being

The concept of well-being was first mentioned by Greek philosophers like Aristotle, Plato, Epicurus and many more (Waterman, 1993), many of them mainly focused on the role of happiness in human existence and developed many definitions based on different doctrines to the extent of creating confusion (Creusier, 2013a). The interest in clarifying well-being is growing both among psychology and management researchers since it constitutes a key point in human resources management improvement, nevertheless, it remains difficult to find a precise definition for it.

Historically, well-being has two important theoretical and philosophical aspects eudaimonism and hedonism (Bhullar et al., 2013). Eudaimonia or Eudaimonism has generated great interest among psychologists, however, its most appropriations are attributed to Aristotle as he described it in detail in his primary ethical text "The Nicomachean Ethics" (Fowers, 2016) on which he regarded "eudaimon" as a substitute of the expression "eu zên" meaning "living well" (Vittersø, 2016); Eudaimonia is often translated as happiness though some have considered that this translation is misleading and absurd (Brown, 2009; Russell, 2010; Sumner, 2002) since happiness is more than a subjective feeling and eudaimonia is not an emotion, it is more a constant state of being. Literally, the parts of the word translate into well 'Eu' and spirit 'Daimon', that has given rise to other proposed translations like 'living well', 'well-being', 'flourishing' or 'fulfilment' (Vittersø, 2016); Eudaimonia has been defined and interpreted in different ways, according to Aristotle, eudaimonia is 'the "pursuit of virtue, excellence, and the best within us" (Huta & Waterman, 2014; Waterman, 1990), as per Donaldson *et al* the eudaimonism component, referred to as psychological well-being, is conceptualized as the search for the attainment of meaning, self-actualization and personal growth (Donaldson et al., 2015).

On the other hand, hedonism has also a distinguished philosophical history, it was mainly developed by Epicurus and Plato, for them the purpose of life is the search for maximum pleasure

and the avoidance of pain and suffering. It can be defined as the doctrine that views pleasure as an intrinsic good and the proper goal of all human action (*Hedonism Defined - APA Dictionary of Psychology*, n.d.), it is considered as a subjective theory as it states that well-being is constituted by pleasant states of consciousness and that everything that contributes to well-being will certainly contribute to pleasure (Tiberius & Hall, 2010). In the context of hedonic psychology, hedonism have been widely associated with Subjective Well-being (SWB), albeit it can be integrated into a more eudaimonic approach (Deci & Ryan, 2008).

Figure N°1: Well-being related concepts from Eudaimonism and Hedonism literature

Source: Authors' own processing.

Hence, both paradigms have tackled well-being (figure1), each from a different perspective; while eudaimonism is all about realizing human potential power and engagement, hedonism is mainly pleasure and happiness oriented (Bhullar et al., 2013; Pradhan & Hati, 2022). These theories have contributed to a better understanding of the well-being at a psychological level, highlighting three main contemporary conceptions of well-being: happiness, satisfaction, or quality of life.

In fact, it's important to clarify these three concepts, as they are used interchangeably when discussing well-being in literature (Voyer & Boyer, 2001). The table below is an attempt to explain each concept:

Table N°1: The three most used concepts in Well-being

Happiness	Satisfaction	Quality of life (QoL)
<p>Happiness is the result of being healthy, both physically and morally, especially after a great effort made by individuals, a group, or an organisation.</p> <p>The largest divide is between hedonic views of happiness as pleasant feelings and favourable judgments vs eudaimonic views of happiness involving doing what is virtuous, morally right, true to oneself, meaningful, and/or growth producing (Fisher, 2010; Ryan & Deci, 2001)</p>	<p>Satisfaction is a feeling of accomplishment felt by the person (individual) after having accomplished tasks or goals in life.</p> <p>It's “an overall assessment of feelings and attitudes about one’s life at a particular point in time ranging from negative to positive.”(Beutell, 2006)</p>	<p>It can be defined as a good and respectful standard of living. QoL has intersections with biological and functional concepts, such as health status, functional status and disability; social and psychological concepts like well-being, satisfaction and happiness (Panzini et al., 2017)</p>

Source: Authors’ processing from (Voyer & Boyer, 2001)

Moreover, more specific theories have been developed to complement the general hedonic and eudaimonic theories, providing more and focused clarification of well-being:

- ❖ **Theory of cognitive adaptation** : It assume that people can adjust their level of happiness in response to events ; and that they can cope with threats in their lives by creating a set of positive illusions, which serve to protect their psychological health. (Taylor & Brown, 1988, 1994) cited in (Czajkowska, 2017).

- ❖ **Theory of standards:** It involves comparing a current state with a given standard. These standards can be:

Comparison of one’s own social status with that of others

The difference between the intended goal and the achieved goal (influenced by the degree of aspiration involved)

The way in which an event is interpreted in relation to the context created by the individual's experiences (Bilmes, 1986).

- ❖ **Goal Theory:** Known as goal setting theory, it is rooted in the old idea of needs and purposes: an individual happiness dwells in their needs' satisfactions, and of course that depends on the nature of needs (needs classification has been explained by A. Maslow, 1954). There are many approaches for this theory, but it is accepted by all that happiness and well-being is best reached when our goals are in harmony in harmony with each other and we are making progress towards achieving them (Bouffard & Lapierre, 1997).
- ❖ **Social Cognitive theory:** It addresses that one's well-being and satisfaction is related to his/her terms of commitment to a valued future and the steps they take to realize that. The state of well-being is largely determined by life objectives. (Bandura, 2011)

Well-being was initially studied as a generic and stable concept, independently from any specific life domains like work for example (Kashdan et al., 2008) (Creusier, 2013b). However, recent literature defends the specificity of well-being at work and the need to use dedicated constructs (Creusier, 2013a; DiPietro et al., 2020; Pradhan & Hati, 2022). Employee or workplace well-being has been defined by several scholars as presented in the following table:

Table N°2: Well-being defined

Author	Definitions
Andrews and Withey (1976)	Well-being is the outcome of one's having perception on her/his situation in line with their needs, values or aspirations; subjective (or hedonic) well-being is considered as a composition of both cognitive evaluation and positive/negative effects (Andrews & Crandall, 1976).

<p>Diener and Eunkook Suh (1997, p.200)</p>	<p>Well-being can be defined by people’s conscious experiences – in terms of hedonic feelings or cognitive satisfactions.</p> <p>Life satisfaction, pleasant affects and unpleasant affects are the three interdependent factors of subjective well-being. Affect refers to pleasant and unpleasant moods and emotions, while life satisfaction refers to cognitive evaluation of satisfaction in life.(Diener & Suh, 1997)</p>
<p>Kahn and Juster (2002, p.630)</p>	<p>“Surveys about well-being are based on one of the three definitions : (1) life satisfaction, (2) health and ability/disability, and (3) composite indices of positive functioning (Kahn & Juster, 2002).</p>
<p>Pollard and Lee (2003, p.60)</p>	<p>“well-being is a complex and multi-faced process of improving personal health and wellness of people”, this concept is constantly gaining researchers’ interest.(Pollard & Lee, 2003)</p>
<p>Lopez <i>et al</i> (2020, p 1365)</p>	<p>“Well-being is defined as an effort to improve ourselves and fulfil our potential, which is related with having a purpose in life and sense of life, coping with challenges and making a certain effort to overcome and achieve valuable goals”(López et al., 2020).</p>
<p>World Health Organization (2022)</p>	<p>“A state of every individual employee to understand his own capability, t manage with the normal stresses of life, to work productively and is able to make a contribution to her/his community”(World Health Organization, 2022)</p>

Source: Authors’ own processing.

Hence, Employee well-being is becoming an important concern for organizations and organizational behaviour researchers, a plethora of research has been examining its importance at an organizational, psychological, and personal sides of employees' life; It becomes a critical factor for organizational success and performance (Kundi et al., 2021), likewise, several studies have shown that employee's well-being leads to various outcomes such as a better workplace performance and productivity, employee engagement, customer satisfaction (Kundi et al., 2021), stress-coping behaviour, mental and physical health, and work attendance (Pradhan & Hati, 2022). Employee Well-being can be categorized in three distinct ways: Psychological well-being, which refers to an employee's psychological needs, life well-being, which refers to an employee's personal life and well-being within that context, and workplace well-being, which refers to an employee's feeling regarding their work life (Bilmes, 1986).

Since critical factors for organisations should be monitored and managed, well-being also should be measured considering that organizations that focus on well-being will be able to develop an competitive advantage in the long run (Wright, 2006), undoubtedly the state of well-being in workplace can be assessed through KPIs (key performance indicators) namely absenteeism, turnover, illness (Pradhan & Hati, 2022), results, delays and more. Although there are other ways that enables to measure the well-being in the workplace such as annual surveys, engagement surveys, Employee Net Promoter Score (ENPS), quality of life policy evaluation. In fact, the engines for employees well-being enhancement can be the mentioned elements mentioned in the hedonism and eudaimonism theories (happiness, suffering removal, virtues...), as well as interpersonal relationships, usefulness, interesting job and tasks, opportunities for progress, skills match, job security, work life balance, working schedule(de Neve, 2018) and more.

1.2. Workplace Performance

The world of work is changing at a remarkable pace, with every industrial revolution, automation and new technologies are taking over, changing the established ideas about work, the economy and even the human nature are evolving accordingly (Litchfield, 2021). By referring to workplace we mean the location and the environment or conditions where people perform their tasks, jobs, and projects for their employer, in other terms we talk about the physical and organizational environment in which employees operate and work; this physical environment features might affect directly workers which creates a need to integrate workspace considerations into core business decision-making (Vischer, 2007).

Workplace evolution has occupied the interest of researchers as well as designers, from private offices, cubicles, and open plans to coworking spaces, managed offices, group offices, moveable furniture, and immersive work environment; this evolution carry out challenges in the quality of workplace environment, and most managers make decisions about these spaces whether they are aware or not of how a tiny change can directly impact the environment, productivity, and performance.

Likewise, the improvement of workplace performance and productivity is becoming a central issue in human resources development and organizational behaviour (OB) research (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). A workplace or employee performance system is imperative for organizations as it should be aligned with business strategy, policies and development perspectives (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). Performance can be viewed as behavioural engagement from an expected outcome, or as a set of individual behaviours or actions that contribute to the achievement of organizational goals (Coffey et al., 1999; Pradhan & Jena, 2017); thereupon we can assume that performance is the result of an task's execution, it can be a positive result as it can be negative (bad/low performance).

Additionally, this workplace performance can be either economic, social or environmental (Reynaud,2003) cited in (Renaud & Berland, 2007), each accomplished task (positive result) will impact the organization economically (more efficiency and efficacy, goal meeting, satisfied customers, and more), environmentally (decrease of more generated direct costs from delays and repetitiveness, decrease of waste, gain of market share and more), and socially (increased employee motivation, well-being and satisfactions, feeling of fulfilment and more) and vice versa each uncompleted or not done well tasks will impact negatively all elements mentioned above. Wherefore it is important for managers to monitor each of these workplace performance indicators towards a global performance (figure 2).

Figure N°2: Workplace global performance -

Source: Model from Reynaud,2003 cited in (Renaud & Berland, 2007)

Workplace performance refers to a workspace whose explicit objective is to support the performance of work, a better workplace is designed to optimize employee’s productivity, offer physical, functional, and psychological comfort (figure3) (Vischer, 2007):

Physical comfort: provided by ensuring basic human needs at workplace such as safety, hygiene, and accessibility.

Functional comfort: provided by ensuring good work conditions and which might be appropriate lighting, available meeting rooms and facilities, quality work tools, and more.

These elements play a huge role is workplace satisfaction.

Psychological comfort: provided by ensuring employees engagement, creating a feeling of belonging and control over one’s workspace. Unquestionably any diminish in the above criteria will lead to a discomfort at the workplace and therefore to a decrease in the global performance. Workplace performance can be measured via : KPI’s (key performance indicators), an overall area of quantifiable measurement using different data gathering sources like questionnaire, observations, human resources databases withing the organisation; at this point it is important to

Figure N°3: Workplace performance and comfort

Source: Authors’ processing from (López et al., 2020)

select relevant and logical KPI's to display the link between what is measured and the potential impact on the physical, functional and psychological workplace environment, this will allow managers to monitor closely the workplace performance and react against this background. The KPI's that can be placed at this level are health KPI's, employee retention, turnovers, tasks/projects delays and even sales and goals achievement rates(O'Neill, 2007).

Next, Workplace Balanced ScoreCard (WBS), is a way of organising relevant KPI's according to company's industry, market, and strategic objectives; each heading within the WBS represents a 'metric', and these KPI's should be directly related to contributions that the workplace makes in supporting behaviours and business processes. An example of this KPI's can be Real Estate and facilities/services that groups used, work environment/behaviour wellness and leadership/customer needs (O'Neill, 2007).

Another method of measurement can be The Workplace Measurement process, it's a methodology that allows to connect the impacts of workplace design features to changes in measures of behaviours, performance, health, and business process, and that using precised KPI's like employee attraction, merit review scores, sense of community, medical claims, psychological stress, innovation, customer satisfaction and considerably more. To conduct this method it's necessary to follow in order some steps: define and measure the KPI's, start workplace redesign, analyse the impacts, improve and then control (O'Neill, 2007).

Measuring workplace performance should be an indispensable method for managers to enhance collaboration, comfort and job control within their organisation and teams, notably that we are in an age where not only individuals that have to adapt to the work conditions but organisations also, since the concept of 'a job for life' is no longer existing (Litchfield, 2021), and that workplace performance is becoming more and more associated with the psychological state and mental health of employees.

1.3. Employee well-being and organisational performance

As previously noted, we will ground our conceptual basis on the utility approach, which considers people's behaviour as a tendency to insure the best state of satisfaction; therefore, "the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people" (Bentham, 1996). Philosophically, this human internal will which manifests itself in getting the best conditions of felicity and happiness in life in general, and at work in particular, is reflective of the balance of utility principle, each person has inside, which consists of maximizing utility over suffering; the amount of happiness over the amount of unhappiness, satisfaction over dissatisfaction (Bentham, 1996).

Deloitte and Viadeo (2017) have conducted a study arguing that 56% of French employees believe that the sense of work is deteriorating (Négaret, 2018). In the same year, another institute confirms that 44% of French Employees do not find a sense in their work (*Observatoire Spinoza*, n.d.). In contrast, the quality of interpersonal relationships has been one of the key factors contributing to the overall well-being at work (de Neve, 2018).

In this context, un-dogmatically speaking, researchers must be open to the hypothesis of having enforced employees, as part of a Taylorism approach, which similarly could be in positive association with work performance: this possibility cannot be ignored. In fact, it cannot be unproductive the traditional school of Taylorism, as well as its supporters – all things being equal.

The main idea of this paper is to mainly discuss a well-being-based performance that finds its inner philosophy, on the one hand, in the meaning of life, as well as internal perception that employees could have about themselves and their environment. And, on the other, in the optimistic conception suggesting that happy employees are more preferred, for corporate outcomes, than unhappy ones. In fact, the literature admits that the best practices of management are beneficial to employees' well-being and are just as much for organizational performance (Korpela et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2007; Saridakis & Cooper, 2016).

A good state of well-being, or at least a collective perception of it (Mullin 2005) cited in (Hellriegel, 2010), could only be a source of motivation and satisfaction for employees, and a springboard onto work productivity afterwards. Ultimately, well-being would be one of the key synonyms of satisfaction, which should be in turn a direct link to work performance. In this framework, the term “well-being” which is compared to health – as previously put by the WHO (World Health Organization, 2022). This dimension of well-being encompasses both the physical and attitudinal levels and should be in line with work performance. It would be hard for a company to imagine working with ill employees for example, that is, the antonym of will being is ill-being (Headey et al., 1984).

Companies reap what they sow; taking care of employees by ensuring the best conditions of well-being is always a HR strategic investment, which expects a return on investment (ROI) afterwards. This latter could take the shape of many contributions, at the daily productive level, or at the commercial level. Satisfied employees will most likely spread positive energy about their company.

2. Methods

The data of this study was collected from eight companies, operating in the food industry in the region of Larache, and one in the metallurgy industry – Morocco, chosen as a first step towards understanding the phenomenon across the country. The open-ended questionnaire concerned Managers and employees, both male and female, of each companies whose staff number exceeds 300 employees and that were chosen through a convenience sampling (non-probability sampling). The main reason for requesting managers to answer was to extract their personal perception about a well-being-based performance, and examine whether HR conditions were facilitators for well-being, and whether the state of well-being pushes them to be more productive, and to evaluate these conditions and well-being measures, fourteen questions were addressed to employees on this matter. The questionnaire content was processed, analysed, and interpreted according to a qualitative method as part of an interpretivist approach. We have chosen this epistemological posture thanks to the subjective and attitudinal nature of the topic, which treats a qualitative phenomenon that deals mainly with people's personal emotions and imaginations in a quite subjective manner. On the other hand, aspects such as observation and documentation were not given. Hence, the only channel of the research was to engineer a questionnaire that externalizes relevant data in line with the research purpose. The team's mission was to explain the questionnaire and then to interpret its result based on an objective reasoning for the purpose of having a close insight on the relationship between well-being and workplace performance at the companies in the region of Larache, Morocco, aiming to expand in further our research on a national scale.

We have chosen unanimously to orient our compass towards the agro-food sector, because we are interested in its evolution, and also because it depends immensely on the human workforce in its productive processes; the thing that will allow us to visualize the state of well-being that orbits around this population. Also, we have taken Larache as an empirical ground because it has significant agricultural potential that is attractive to investors, and to which we are keen to explore.

Whereas quantitative research seeks to validate a theory by conducting an experiment and analysing the results numerically, qualitative research seeks to arrive at a theory that explains the behaviour observed (Lowhorn, 2007). In this way, it can be said that quantitative research is more deductive and qualitative research is more inductive (Trochim, W.M.K. 2000). In recent times, some researchers, both students and established academic staff, take a pragmatic approach when designing studies by incorporating components of quantitative methods in their

research to offset any bias against a wholly qualitative study (Hameed, 2020). Based on the desired outcome of the research, social scientists may choose between quantitative or qualitative designs (Lowhorn, 2007). Thus, the researcher must choose the method of inquiry that is most appropriate to his subject and his field, rather than trying to position himself compared to an epistemological current or another (Tijani, 2011).

The importance of an interpretivist approach manifests itself in the fact that it allows the researcher to oscillate between the knowledge already present in the literature and the horizon it seeks to discover with empirical studies. This round trip allowed us to empower the relevance of our scientific outcomes, avoid scientific bias, and ultimately generalize the research results worldwide.

3. Result and Discussion

In the first phase of study, we examined the available literature regarding employee well-being and workplace performance. In the second phase, we aimed to interpret the open-ended survey with the aim of finding out whether managers and employees recognize the importance of employee well-being at work, and they are making efforts to improve it, and whether they are using any measurement tools. At this level we will provide a detailed analysis of the survey's results and a general finding of this research.

The open-ended survey is divided into three parts: (1) general information, (2) questions about well-being, and (3) questions about well-being and workplace performance. Concerning the first part result, in our sample most respondents were female employees (66% against 33%), most of the employees are aged between 20 and 35 years old (71%). In terms of organizations, the majority have more than 300 employees (42%) which shows that most companies are SMEs (medium-sized enterprises), and 90% of these companies operate in the agricultural sector.

Second- and third-part results are presented in the following table (see next page) :

Table N°3: Results and Interpretations

Questions/Key points	Explanation	Results	Interpretation
1. Workspace	The workspace can either help in enhancing the well-being or in worsen it. It's an important element to consider when talking about workplace environment and well-being.	66,7% - Open space 19,00% Collaborative office 9,50%: Individual closed office 4,8%: No precised work office	Majority of companies prefer not to separate employees to avoid disparity and help them develop relationships.
2. Satisfaction regarding job position	Job satisfaction is crucial in developing employee well-being.	71.40% of the employees are satisfied with their job positions 28,60% are not satisfied.	Companies are making remarkable efforts to satisfy their employees by providing the right job opportunities for the right candidates.
3. The state in which employees feel comfortable (in groups/project groups/individually)	Work mode preferences reflects if the employees are on good terms.	52.4% of the employees prefer to work in a team while 28.6% prefer to work individually and the rest (19%) prefer to work in a team but only with the project team members.	Most of employees prefer to work in teams. That can either reflect that they have good relationships with their team members which motives them more, or they find working in teams will be more efficient in term of results and knowledge sharing.
4. The quality of the provided work tools	Work tools impact directly the employee well-being (for example slow computer and internet)	81% of employees are satisfied with the work tool they have/use, while 19% are not satisfied.	-
5. The elements that influence the most the	each employee has an element that can influence their well-being and	40.5% of employees find that the relationship with colleagues	This shows that the most important factor that impacts the employees'

<p>well-being at work (in a positive way)</p>	<p>comfort at work, we wanted to know which of the proposed elements has the most impact, we left an empty text zone in case there is more to add.</p>	<p>has a real influence on their comfort and well-being at work, while 24.9% of them find that the workspace has the most influence, 19.6% find that it is the quality of the office design, 7.6% find that the main influencing factor is the absence of noise, but 5.8% find that it can be the air-conditioning or the state of the office furniture, and 1.6% find that it is the existence of resting space that influences.</p>	<p>well-being of employees is the social context within the organization, for example the relationships between employees can create a favourable climate for them and for the company to reduce the risk of delaying a project due to problems between colleagues.</p>
<p>6. Feeling bored at work</p>	<p>Boredom can be a direct factor when it comes to evaluating the well-being. Being bored is considered as a bad state.</p>	<p>47.5% of the workers feel bored at work while 52.5% of the workers do not get that feeling.</p>	<p>Majority find pleasure in doing their job.</p>
<p>7. Access to spaces</p>	<p>Access to spaces like restaurant, coffee corners...etc can ameliorate the well-being at work.</p>	<p>30.5% of employees have access to a coffee corner, as 30.3% have a gym access, while 20.2% have a friendly sharing space, 10.5% of employees have access to a restaurant or cafeteria within the company, while 8.5% have a games room and the rest have nothing at all.</p>	<p>This shows that the company is making a remarkable effort and in an indirect way by providing access to spaces to refresh the mood and bring employees together.</p>

<p>8. Employees' opinion regarding the services and activities provided by the company and whether they find them as a source of performance enhancement.</p>		<p>85.7% of the employees find the services and activities provided by the company as a source of performance improvement as it helps them to refresh their mood, while 14.3% find the services and activities provided by the company as not a source of performance improvement.</p>	<p>That shows that the employees are aware of companies' efforts to improve their well-being and performance.</p>
<p>9. The most fascinating/important aspect of your current work</p>	<p>Each employee has a different view of work. Some think that the localisation is the most important factor in choosing a job position, while others think that development and learning opportunities are way more important. As explained above goals can be source of well-being boosting depending on person's perspective.</p>	<p>42.4% of the employees find the interest in work is the most motivating element, while 18.1% find that the quality of work life is more important, 12.9% think it is the level of remuneration that makes work better, and 10.3% of the employees find the location and the training offered is the most fascinating elements when considering a job. 11.5% find that development opportunities are the fascinating elements, or the responsibility and the rest (4.8%) choose</p>	<p>-</p>

		the company's reputation as a motivating element.	
10. The use of well-being measurement tools	Measurement tools provide an overview of the given importance to employees' well-being.	66.7% of companies do not use well-being measures at work, whereas 33.3% of companies measure the well-being.	That shows that most companies do not take into consideration yet the importance of well-being as an indicator in workplace performance.
11. The most encouraging and motivating aspect for a good performance:	Knowing what motivates and encourages employees help in determining the engines of their well-being.	42.4% of the employees find that the most motivating element is the health and quality of life at work, as well as 41.4% find that what motivates the most of them is the salary, 8.8% find that it is the place of work, but 7.4% think that it can be either the climate of the workplace or the encouragements they receive.	That shows that the salary and a healthy workplace are the most motivating elements at work.
12. Barriers/Obstacles to performance	Obstacles and barriers in term of performance can be demotivating and might worsen the well-being at work.	85.7% of employees are experiencing obstacles that impact their performance while 14.3% of employees do not have any obstacles/barriers.	That indicates that most employees are finding obstacles in their current jobs.
13. The most experienced Obstacles	It is important to identify the obstacles, since any barrier to performance	25.3%: poor management	Majority are having problems with workload and short/quick deadlines.

	will be also a barrier to a better well-being.	41.2%: fewer team member with over workload 11.8%: slow technology 14.4%: workload, short deadlines 7.3%: lack of flexibility in terms of place and time of work (e.g., the location of the workplace and distance from home),	
14. Techniques used to tackle and eliminate the obstacles	Techniques reflects if employees opt for alternatives and problem-solving skills, or they just stand still in face of barriers.	15% of employees prefer to ask for help, 45% choose time management; 30% prefer to manage the stress, to refocus on the required tasks, but 10% did not use any of these techniques.	Stress and time management are the most used techniques in eliminating/avoiding more obstacles.

Source: Authors' own processing

Based on the knowledge acquired in our literature review, and the results of the survey in which majority of respondents admit that employee well-being is key factor in improving workplace performance, we can conclude that there is a strong link between employee well-being and workplace performance. Indeed, well-being at work result from company's efforts to boost it, but also the employee to recognize these efforts. Most of companies choose to operate using open spaces with the aim of improving relationships among employees since interpersonal relationships have a sizeable and significant positive effect on job satisfaction of the average employees, therefore their well-being (de Neve, 2018). Furthermore, according to the respond-

ents we can assume the importance of having quality work tools and equipments and convenient spaces to boost the well-being at workplace and avoid boredom. Besides, employee's motivation efforts must be both mental: creating the proper work conditions and material: providing a good salary as most employees consider the remuneration as the major source of job satisfaction.

In addition, majority the studied companies do not use well-being measure tools despite their importance in observing workplace performance and eliminating all risks that can impact it negatively, particularly that employees are dealing with many obstacles (question 13). Measuring tools are important to ameliorate working conditions and understand better the workplace environment, they can be of a great help to managers to observe their teams and react in the right time. Thus, measures and indicators can contribute in building a healthy work culture within organisations by reducing stress and chances of developing mental and physical illnesses (less absenteeism and hospital visits), ensuring a good life-work balance and more employee engagement all will result in a better employee devotion performance : A healthy and contented employee can go extra miles in his job(Pradhan & Hati, 2022).

Above all, workplace performance cannot be achieved and maintained without ensuring an environment where transparent communication is possible, mental health is given an importance and employees' efforts are valued, especially that we are in an era where people are becoming more and more sensitive after the Covid-19 pandemic (the rise in both anxiety and depressive disorders at more than 25% during the first year of the pandemic (World Health Organization, 2022)).

Conclusion

This study enabled us to clarify more the relationship between employee well-being and workplace performance by providing clear understanding of the two concepts and approaching them from both a theoretical and empirical point of view. From a theoretical perspective, many researchers and academics have emphasized the strong impact of employees' well-being on workplace performance and subsequently on firms' global performance. Assuredly, from an empirical perspective, the responses collected from the eight organizations in the region of Larache allowed us to affirm that employee's well-being and workplace performance are strongly associated aspects in business conduct, investing in improving employees' well-being will result always in having a motivated team and good performance. Moreover, in today's competitive business environment, remuneration was and will be a source of motivation, however with the

rising challenges to boost the well-being, job satisfaction, and motivation, remuneration should be combined with non-monetary rewards and assets.

This study had led us to conclude that (1) all companies in the region of Larache are making efforts to improve the well-being of their employees by giving access to the quality work tools and equipments, and facilities that can help them in refreshing their work during and after work hours. (2) Salary and quality of life or environment are the elements that encourage the most employees to give invest their full potential in the workplace performance. (3) to help employees to complete their tasks quickly and efficiently it is important to either to give appropriate deadlines or to help them arrange well their tasks according to the urgency. (4) finally, the success of organization requires a mutual collaboration and contribution from both employers and employees: the employers need to value the work and efforts of their employees, and on the other side, employees need to be productive to achieve a better work performance. However, the results cannot be generalized due to the size of our sample, our main goal was to detect if these concepts are being used and spoken about in the business world and to explore the relationship between the two variables, well-being and workplace performance, on a regional level in furtherance of broadening the research on a national level.

In brief, a happy healthy workplace environment will improve employees 'psychological health and help them to contribute more in achieving the strategic goals of a business, if we take into account the time employees spend at work (average of 44hours/week), employers should provide all necessary implements for a better well-being and performance.

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